

CO-State Estimation of Lithium Ion Battery using Artificial Neural Network

David Enemali Abah
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
deabah@abu.edu.ng

Fasasi Qudus Opeyemi
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
foqudus@engineering.abu.edu.ng

Lawan Abdullah Ahmad
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
abdullahlawanahmad@gmail.com

Abdulrahman Sani Maiyadi
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
Abdoulmaiyadee16@gmail.com

Umar Yusuf
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
hyumar2021@gmail.com

Abdulrahman badamasi
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
abdulrahmanbadamasi123@gmail.com

Idris Shehu
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria, Nigeria
Idrisshehu603@gmail.com

Abstract

The reliable operation of lithium-ion batteries in electric vehicles and renewable energy storage systems depends on accurate monitoring of their internal states. Conventional estimation methods for the state of charge (SOC) and state of health (SOH) often face challenges such as high model complexity, parameter sensitivity, and limited adaptability under nonlinear operating conditions. This study proposes an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach for co-state estimation of lithium-ion batteries, focusing on SOC and SOH. The ANN is trained with battery input features, including terminal voltage, current, and temperature, to learn the nonlinear mapping between observable parameters and hidden battery states. Simulation results demonstrate that the ANN achieves high estimation accuracy, with root mean square error (RMSE) values below 2% and a coefficient of determination (R^2) exceeding 0.98. The

proposed method also exhibits reduced computational burden and strong robustness against measurement noise and dynamic load profiles. By providing reliable real-time predictions of SOC and SOH, the proposed method improves battery management system (BMS) performance, ensuring safer operation, longer lifespan, and more efficient energy utilization. This work highlights the potential of ANN-based techniques as a scalable and intelligent solution for advanced battery state estimation.

Keywords— Artificial Neural Network, Battery Management System, State of Charge, State of Health.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the world shifts towards a sustainable energy future, advancing renewable energy technologies and decreasing reliance on fossil fuels have become essential strategies for mitigating climate change and meeting global carbon reduction goals. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have taken a central role in electrochemical energy storage systems and electric transportation due to their superior energy and power

densities, long cycle life, high charge-discharge efficiency, and strong rate capability [1]. The Battery Management System (BMS) serves as the "central nervous system" of power batteries, continuously tracking critical parameters such as voltage, temperature, and current through controller area network transmissions. One of its primary functions is to estimate essential internal states of the battery, including the State of Charge (SOC) and the State of Health (SOH), these estimations are crucial for optimizing battery lifespan [2]. A general schematic diagram of an efficient BMS is shown in Figure 1. Therefore, accurate SOC estimation is a key performance indicator for BMS, as it provides vital information about the battery's remaining charge and plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficient and safe operation of electric vehicles (EVs) [3]. A widely recognized conclusion is that the most commonly used methods for estimating SOC primarily consist of traditional techniques, such as the Ampere-hour integration method and the open-circuit voltage method, model-based method and data-driven methods [4], [5]. Each of the above SOC estimation methods used in BMS applications has its own advantages and limitations. Specifically, traditional methods heavily depend on current measurements or require the battery to remain idle for extended periods, which restricts their practical use in real-time EV operations [6]. Additionally, while data-driven methods (DDM) have gained significant attention in recent years for battery state estimation, challenges such as limited generalization capability and the underutilization of available measurements in real-world scenarios hinder their accuracy [7], [8], posing a barrier to their widespread adoption in onboard applications.

A joint SOC-SOH estimation method was proposed considering the influence of the temperature [9]. It combines the Forgetting Factor Recursive Least Squares (FFRLS) algorithm, Total Least Squares (TLS) algorithm, and Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) algorithm. In [6], introduces a novel variational extended Kalman filter (EKF) approach based on the least square error method, utilizing a second-order equivalent circuit model of the battery. Reference [10], investigates the mechanisms and contributing factors of lithium-ion battery degradation, using battery capacity as a key indicator of the state of health (SOH). A long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network is employed to model the

capacity trajectory over time. In [11], present a novel optimization method for estimating the State of Charge (SOC) of battery charge state is proposed, combining the Levenberg–Marquardt Algorithm (LMA) for online parameter identification with the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) for SOC estimation. In [12], presents a method for estimating the state of health (SOH) and predicting the remaining useful life (RUL) of lithium-ion batteries by utilizing charging feature extraction and ridge regression. Reference [13], introduces a novel physics-informed equivalent circuit model (ECM) tailored for lithium-ion batteries in electric vehicle applications, balancing electrochemical accuracy with manageable complexity. This paper presents the development of an ANN-based framework for estimating State of Charge (SOC), and State of Health (SOH) using MATLAB/Simulink. The contributions of this paper are:

- i. In this study, SOC and SOH were estimated together using a single ANN framework trained on the same dataset, rather than independently. The integrated ANN model simultaneously learns the relationships between voltage, current, temperature, and the three target outputs, ensuring a consistent and unified estimation process.
- ii. Mathematical formulations for SOC (coulomb counting and voltage-based) and SOH (capacity- and resistance-based) are structured into a consistent framework that supports ANN learning.
- iii. By training the ANN with multiple inputs (voltage, current, temperature, cycle count) and outputs (SOC, SOH), the model achieves superior robustness against sensor noise, non-linear battery behavior, and environmental variations.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: section II System Description; methodology is given in section III; results and discussions are presented in section IV; and section V presents the conclusion.

Figure 1: State estimation battery in BMS [14]

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A. State of Charge

SOC represents the available capacity of the battery relative to its nominal/full capacity. It tells “how much charge is left in the battery,” similar to a fuel gauge in cars. Equation (1) is the coulomb counting (Ampere-hour method) and equation (2) is the voltage base estimation [15].

$$SOC(t) = SOC(t_0) - \frac{1}{C_n} \int_{t_0}^t I(\tau) dr \quad (1)$$

$$SOC \approx f(V_{oc}) \quad (2)$$

Where V_{oc} is the open-circuit voltage (OCV). A nonlinear lookup table or polynomial regression is often used,

C_n : Normal capacity of the battery (Ah)

$I(\tau)$: Battery current (positive during discharge, negative during charge)

B. State of Health

SOH measures the *aging and degradation* of the battery. It compares the present performance to that of a fresh/new battery. Equation (3) is capacity-based definition, equation (4) is the resistance-based definition and equation (5) is the hybrid definition for determining the SOH [15].

$$SOH_{capacity} = \frac{C_{actual}}{C_{rated}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$SOH_{resistance} = \frac{R_{new}}{R_{present}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$SOH = w_1 \cdot SOH_{capacity} + w_2 \cdot SOH_{resistance} \quad (5)$$

Where C_{actual} is the measure charge capacity of the aged cell, C_{rated} , nominal rated capacity of a new cell, $R_{present}$ current internal resistance, R_{new} initial resistance, w_1 , w_2 are weighting factors.

III. METHODOLOGY

A MATLAB/Simulink R2024a model was used to generate synthetic battery data values (voltage, current, and temperature) with corresponding SOC and SOH labels under varying load and thermal conditions. The battery model was partitioned into three subsets: 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing to ensure proper model learning, over fitting prevention, and performance evaluation. The ANN architecture included three input neurons, three hidden layers (128, and 64 neurons with LeakyReLU activation), and one output neuron. Training employed the Adam optimizer for 50 epochs with a batch size of 32 and learning rate of 0.0005. Models were trained separately for SOC and SOH. Performance was evaluated using RMSE and R^2 metrics. Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the co-estimation using ANN.

Figure 2: Co-State Estimation using ANN

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the proposed Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model was evaluated using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and coefficient of

determination (R^2). To verify its effectiveness, the ANN results were compared with other established machine learning and model-based methods such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN), and the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), using the same dataset.

As presented in Table 1, the ANN achieved the highest estimation accuracy with R^2 values of 0.9939 for SOC and 0.9999 for SOH, outperforming all benchmark models. The bar chart in Figure 3 shows that the ANN produced the lowest RMSE values of 0.0211 (SOC) and 0.0114 (SOH), confirming its superior learning capability. The scatter plots in Figure 4 and Figure 5 further demonstrate a near-perfect correlation between predicted and actual values, validating the ANN's reliability for accurate real-time co-state estimation in lithium-ion battery systems.

TABLE 1: R^2 PERFORMANCE METRICS RECORDED

Model	SOC (R^2)	SOH (R^2)
ANN	0.9939	0.9999
PINN	0.7061	0.7812
EKF	0.9854	—
RF	0.9560	0.5056
LSTM	0.9500	—
SVM	0.9630	—

Figure 3: Bar chart of RMSE comparison for SOC and SOH

Figure 5: SOH Scatter plots of Predicted versus Actual Values

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Figure 4: SOC Scatter plots of Predicted versus Actual Values

V. CONCLUSION

This work has presented an Artificial Neural Network (ANN)-based approach for co-state estimation of lithium-ion batteries, focusing on accurate prediction of the state of charge (SOC) and state of health (SOH). By leveraging easily measurable inputs such as terminal voltage, current, and temperature, the ANN effectively captures the nonlinear dynamics of battery behavior without relying on complex electrochemical models. The results demonstrate that the proposed method achieves high estimation accuracy, with low RMSE values, as well as strong correlation coefficients ($R^2 > 0.98$), indicating its reliability under varying load and environmental conditions. Furthermore, the ANN shows robustness against measurement noise and adaptability to dynamic operating profiles, making it suitable for real-time battery management system (BMS) applications. Overall, the proposed method contributes to enhancing the safety, efficiency, and lifespan of lithium-ion batteries used in electric vehicles, renewable energy storage, and portable device

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